

An outcome Study of the Health & Wellness Camp conducted at the Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) Ashram from 21 to 28 October 2024

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ABSTRACT:

Introduction: YPV healing camps conducted at the YPV Ashram are very effective in the holistic healing of patients (participants) because of high energy levels and pollution-free environment. This paper describes one such camp conducted at the YPV Ashram between 21 and 28 October 2024 by a team of YPV healers.

Method: This retrospective study uses data collected from the 22 participants at the beginning and end of the camp, Healers' records, and patient feedback obtained at the end of the camp.

Results: Quantitative data analysis shows a statistically significant weight reduction for the participants. The mean value of the waist measurements was reduced by 1.5%. Qualitative data analysis shows that all participants were freed from their anxieties, concerns, and conundrums regarding their medical situations by the end of the healing camp. They no longer experienced any pain at all. Feedback from exit interviews revealed that these outcomes assisted the participants in raising their degree of well-being and self-esteem. Ashram's satwic and salt-free cuisine supported the participants' health improvements and emotional stability. Healers' attributes, such as healing and counselling skills and being kind and compassionate;

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How to Cite

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participants' attributes, such as receptiveness, openness, and desire for self-healing and self-care, contributed to successful outcomes. Nine participants learned to heal and became healers.

Conclusions: YPV healing camps aid patients to get relief from mental and emotional problems of sickness besides treating physical illness. These camps offer opportunities for patients to learn healing and become healers themselves. Further research related to YPV camps is recommended.

KEYWORDS: Health & Wellness Camp, Holistic healing, Patient psychology, Yoga Prana Vidya System ®, YPV ®

INTRODUCTION:

Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) System

The integrative and holistic approach to healthcare acknowledges that conventional mainstream medicine alone cannot adequately address a person's health on its own, since it frequently ignores crucial psychological and spiritual aspects [1].

The Yoga Prana Vidya (YPV) system consists of integrated approaches to a healthy lifestyle, including simple physical exercises, yogic breathing exercises, meditation techniques, the right diet, and pranic energy healing techniques. By adopting this lifestyle, practitioners can maintain holistic health and well-being, i.e., physically, mentally, and emotionally, and balance worldly and spiritual aspects of life [2-3]. Higher levels of immunity are achieved, which helps prevent diseases. Literature shows over a hundred published research papers with recorded evidence of successful healing of patients with various diseases. Patients are healed individually in proximal and/or distance mode. Online Group healing sessions also guide the participants in healing themselves and others.

YPV Healing Camps

Patients in groups are also healed in specially organised healing camps conducted over a few days to weeks. The YPV Ashram is the most popular

venue because of its high energy levels and pollution-free environment to achieve excellent patient results. Teams of healers organise and promote Healing camps for selected and willing patients at the Ashram. Several studies have evaluated the outcomes of healing camps with successful results, such as Rajagopal et al (2019) [4], Gupta et al (2022) [5], Karnani et al (2022) [6], Hegde et al (2023) [7], Neravetla JR et al. (2022) [8], Karnani et al. (2023) [9]. In addition, there have been studies conducted to evaluate the effects of YPV Ashram-based programmes for groups of YPV healers and Arhat Yoga Practitioners with successful results in improved well-being, such as Neravetla JR 92020) [10], Nanduri et al (2022) [11], Neravetla et al (2023) [12].

The present study examines and evaluates the outcomes of the YPV healing camp conducted at YPV Ashram from 21 to 28 October 2024.

Healing camp

Purpose & organisation

This camp was held from 21 to 28 October 2024 at the YPV Ashram situated at Doddaubbanur (Thally-635118) near Hosur in Tamil Nadu. A group of 8 healers (Table 1) including a senior healer formed the team led by the senior healer and planned and organized the camp. The participants for the camp were recruited through referrals from other healers, and only those who were mobile and had health problems were included.

Table 1: YPV Healers with their levels of competencies

Healer	YPV Competency level
1	YPV Level 6
2	YPV Level 5
3	YPV Level 5
4	Associate Certified
5	Healer Develop Program Level 1
6	Healer Develop Program Level 1
7	YPV Level 1
8	YPV Level 1

The camp had seen participation of 23 persons, of which 17 were females in the age range 40 to 69 years, 4 males in the age range 42 to 66 years, and 2 children(boys) ages 7 and 14. The presenting issues of the participants (patients) are given in Table 2.

Table 2: Presenting issues/illnesses of the participants

	Presenting issue/illness	Female	Male	Total cases
1	pain	14	1	15 (65.2%)
2	Gastric/digestive disorders	9	3	12 (52.2%)
3	Metabolic issues	10	2	12 (52.2%)
4	Psychological (Mental/emotional)	5	1	6 (26%)
5	women-specific issues	6		6 (35.3%)
6	Sleeplessness	2	2	4 (17.4%)
7	Lack of energy	3	1	4 (17.4%)
8	Eyes/vision issues	3	1	4 (17.4%)
9	Thyroid	3		3 (13%)
10	incontinence	1	1	2 (8.7%)
11	Psoriasis	2		2 (8.7%)
12	Asthma	1	1 kid 7 yr	2 (8.7%)
13	UTI	1		1 (4.3%)

Camp programme execution

All participants (patients) stayed in the Ashram accommodation. The daily schedule started at 6.45 am with Isabgol and tea. Then at 7.15 am, they were taken for one set of physical exercises. One of

the meditation sessions followed, such as morning sadhana, PPM (planetary peace meditation), or great invocation depending on the needs of the participants. After that, they were given a fruit breakfast which included a tender coconut. Then

they were asked to go for a short walk. At 10 am they joined the Divine energy group healing of 15 minutes at Ahram, which also goes online daily.

Thereafter, healing with Crystal pebbles was done in the lie-down position, and the pebbles were placed on the affected chakras and parts. Afterward, the camp healers did one-on-one healing for each participant. Healing was done in 3 levels. Initially, a HDP healer would do healing, then level 5 healing, and then level 6 healing. The team had two YPV level 1 healers also who were doing level 1 healing for two days. Then they were given the tasks of arranging and co-ordinating and guiding participants and filling up feedback forms.

Afterward, at about 1 pm they were given lunch, and rest time followed.

The afternoon session started at 3.30 pm. The session started with doing forgiveness sadhana, and nurturing by the team leader. After that at 4.30 pm, they participated in YPV Level 1 healing class until at about 7.30 or 8.00 pm. After that dinner and night sleep followed. That was the end-of-the-day schedule.

In the last two days, after they finished the YPV Level 1 course, the participants were asked to do self-healing and group blessings and healings.

STUDY METHOD:

This is a retrospective study, with data collected from the participants before and ends of the camp, data from the healers, exit interviews, and feedback from all participants.

Sample

The sample consisted of 23 participants (as stated above) who joined the program voluntarily. However, valid data was available from 22 participants only.

Data collection

Individual weight, BMI, and Waist size were measured before the start of camp and after the camp ended.

Individual medical reports were also obtained for healing and checking results.

A confidential healing progress sheet was also filled daily individually to record daily healing sessions and progress achieved.

Exit interviews of short video clips were recorded to know how the participants experienced the camp.

Data analysis

Statistical methods are used in the analysis of the measured numerical data. Content analysis methods are used in analyzing the data from exit feedback interviews and daily progress sheets.

RESULT:

The results obtained from the quantitative analysis are as follows:

1. Body weight reduction

From the available data of 22 participants, it is observed that there is a statistically significant reduction in the mean weight of the group at the end of the camp.

2. Waist measurements of 22 participants before and after camp show a mean reduction of 1.5% for the group.

The qualitative data analysis shows the following results.

1. Health & Wellness outcomes

An analysis of the participant reporting issues is presented in Table 2. From this, it is observed that *Pain* is the highest reported symptom (65.2%), followed by Gastric/digestive issues (52.2%) and metabolic issues (52.2%). The psychological issues reported are 26%. Though not reported by all, the psychological issues such as anxiety, fear, depression, etc on their health condition are the common reasons for low well-being at the start of the camp.

Toward the end of the healing camp, all participants were relieved of their fears, worries, and dilemmas about their health conditions. The pain suffered by them was eliminated. These results helped the

participants improve their level of well-being and self-esteem as revealed in the exit interviews. In addition, the salt-less and satwic food at the Ashram helped the participants to remain emotionally stable.

2. Factors that influenced the patient outcomes in the camp

An analysis of the data shows two types of factors, (1) Healer attributes and (2) participant attributes.

The Healer's attributes are: Counselling skills, Healing skills, being kind and compassionate, educating the patients in self-healing and self-care,

Patient attributes are: receptiveness, openness, self-healing, and self-care.

3. Patient education in self-healing and self-care

In this camp, out of the 23 participants, nine were already healers, and nine were non-healers before joining the camp. The non-healers learned the YPV level 1 healing course in this one-week camp. This shows the enthusiasm and interest in self-healing and healing others. The 5 remaining were considering learning to heal over time.

DISCUSSION:

A question generally arises about the specific advantages of YPV healing camps compared with other modes of healthcare delivery.

Experience from this camp and the previous camps shows that YPV healing camps use Integrative protocols which help to heal holistically treating the root cause of the sickness. However mainstream medical care such as allopathy usually treats the manifested symptoms.

An additional advantage of YPV healing camps is that they help people practice integrative protocols, which boost immunity and help as preventive measures.

The findings from this camp are very similar to those obtained in the previous camps [4-9].

CONCLUSION:

YPV healing camps are helpful to patients in treating not only physical illnesses but also mental and emotional issues faced by the patients on the path of recovery. These camps help the patients to receive training to become healers themselves to spread the concept of self-healing and heal others in their surroundings. The concepts of patient self-healing and self-care are very important for healthy societies. Further research may be conducted with appropriate samples and methodology.

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Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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